

Role of (QWL) Quality of Work Life on Employee Retention in Private Sector Companies

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Abstract

Intoday's competitive scenario it is a costly and time taking activity to hire and train an employee and in the due course it is even more difficult to retain the same in the organization. As the WLO (*World Labor Organization*) defines the Qualified Worker as an employee with standard practices laid by the WLO and on the other hand this qualified worker can contribute to a large extent to the respective organization provided that the organization is able to retain the same. It is high time that organizations are learning how to respect the employee's individuality and their commitment to work more effectively and efficiently. Practically speaking Creating high quality of work life increases an organization's value. Quality of working life (QWL) consists of opportunities for active involvement in group working arrangements or problem solving that are of mutual benefit to employees or employers, based on labor management cooperation. People also conceive of QWL as a set of methods, such as autonomous work groups, job enrichment, and high-involvement aimed at boosting the satisfaction and productivity of workers. It entails employee commitment to the organization and an environment in which this commitment can flourish. Providing quality at work not only reduces attrition but also helps in reduced absenteeism and improved job satisfaction. From this study it is further explored that Not only does QWL contribute to a company's ability to recruit quality people, but also it enhances a company's competitiveness. Common beliefs support the contention that QWL will positively nurture a more flexible, loyal, and motivated workforce, which are essential in determining the company's competitiveness.

Introduction

The success of any organization depends to a large extent upon the capability, competence, efficiency, and level of development of human resources, who being the active agents, accumulate capital, exploit natural resources, and build social, economic and political organizations. No

organization can think of viability and effectiveness without the efficient utilization of human resources. Therefore, human resource is the most important resource and is considered the backbone of every organization. Though factors such as exploration of natural resources, availability of physical and financial resources, and international aid contribute to the economic development of a country, none of these factors is more significant than committed manpower. In fact, it may be said that all the development comes from the human mind. It has been observed that the countries endowed with the same level of natural resources, technology, and international aid have a great difference on the front of their development quotient. Their productivity and development mostly depend upon the availability, efficiency and committed human resources.

Today, organizations operate in an environment characterized by technological changes, which in turn, affect employment opportunities, skill requirement, management policies, strategies and style, expectations and aspirations of employees as well as the physical working conditions. In the industrial world, the thrust is now given to “quality” in order to foster a quality culture. Quality assumes a goal or an objective or even a priority. Quality work cannot be achieved easily. Besides, people's issues move to the foreground and technical issues take a supporting role. It is evident from history that work has occupied an important place in the life of human beings. How people have thought and felt about the working experience have also been an age old concern for both workers and managers. With the rapidly changing technological, socio-economic, political, and legal environment, effective management of human resources has become a challenging job. Effective utilization of human resources requires better quality of work life by providing adequate financial compensation, good working conditions, suitable opportunities for growth and development, workers' participation in management and by ensuring social justice in the organization.

Quality of work Life

Robbins (1989) defined QWL as a process by which an organization responds to employee needs by developing mechanisms to allow them to share fully in making the decisions that design their lives at work and Quality of work life is specifically related to the level of happiness a person derives for his career. Walton attributes the evolution of QWL to various phases in history. Legislation enacted in early 20th century to protect employees from job injury and to eliminate working conditions, followed by the unionization movement in the 1930's and 1940's were the initial steps. The emphasis was given on the following factors:

- 1) Working condition
- 2) Job security
- 3) Work place & economic gains
- 4) Positive relationship between morale & productivity
- 5) Equal employment opportunity
- 6) Human needs & expectations
- 7) Relationship between motivation & leadership

QWL has been well recognized as a multi-dimensional construct and it may not be universal or eternal. Each person has different needs when it comes to their careers; the quality level of their work life is determined by whether those needs are being met. While some people might be content with a simple minimum wage job as long as it helps pay the bills, others would find such a job to be too tedious or involve too much physical labor and would find such a position to be highly unsatisfactory.

In brief, QWL includes,

- 1) An opportunity to exercise one's talents and capacities, to face challenges and situations that require independent initiative and self-direction;
- 2) An activity thought to be worthwhile by the individuals involved;
- 3) An activity in which one understands the role the individual plays in the achievement of some overall goals; and
- 4) A sense of taking pride in what one is doing and in doing it well.

Richard E. Walton explains quality of work life in terms of eight broad conditions of employment that constitute desirable quality of work life. He proposed the same criteria for measuring QWL. Those criteria include:

- 1) Adequate and Fair Compensation
- 2) Safe and Healthy Working Conditions
- 3) Opportunity to Use and Develop Human Capacities
- 4) Opportunity for Career Growth
- 5) Social Integration in the Work Force
- 6) Constitutionalism in the Work Organization
- 7) Work and Quality of Life
- 8) Social Relevance of Work

Management Dilemma

In the current global and competitive scenario it can be easily observed that the private sector organizations are facing various challenges, especially in retaining talented employees' i.e. Qualified Workers. The average costs of meeting the high employee turnover are curbing away the profitability of even the wealthiest organizations. Hence the best and brightest of the pool must be selected and retained. If an employee is not satisfied by his job, he/she is always having a second option i.e. may switch over to some other more suitable organization. Hence it is the responsibility of respective organization to retain their best and knowledgeable employees. Thereby an effective employee retention program is required to create and foster an environment that encourages employees to remain employed by having policies and practices in places that address their diverse needs.

As detailed in the above discussion Retention program of the organizations are required to be focused on the following five points:

- 1.Compensation
- 2.Environment
- 3.Growth
- 4.Relationship
- 5.Support to sustain their leadership and growth in the workplace.

The success of any organization depends on how well it addresses their work life issues. The elements that are relevant to an individual's quality of work life include the task, the physical work environment, social environment within the organization, administrative system and relationship between life on and off the job.

A safe and healthy environment is essential in order to extract satisfied performance from the employees. Many organizations are offering flexible work options to their employees wherein employees enjoy flexi-timings for dedicating their efforts at work. The appropriate and attractive salary is one among the important factors used in retaining the talented employees. Providing quality at work not only reduces attrition but also helps in reduced absenteeism and improved job satisfaction thereby helping the organization in retaining their employees. Hence the researchers are interested in studying the effect on quality of work life on employee retention among the employees of private sectors organizations.

Objectives

The objectives of the present study are as follows:

- To study the socio demographic characteristics of the respondents
- To analyze the health and safety provisions pertaining to quality of work life
- To examine the working conditions of the organizations
- To find the relationship between the worker and superior officers
- To understand the satisfaction level of the employees

Research Methodology

For this present study the Descriptive and exploratory research design is used based on demographic and occupational characteristics of the employees. The universe of the study included the employees working in private sectors organization in Jaipur. A sample of total 100 respondents was selected using stratified random sampling. The questionnaire used to collect data contains the questions of Five point Likert scale, dichotomous questions and some with the multiple choices. In this research it has also been tried to find out that if quality of work life has any significant relationship with job related variables and with demographic variables. The present study suffered

from some limitations like small sample size and limited area of investigation which might not be true representative of the whole population of the private sector organizations.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Analysis of Likert Scale Data

Working Environment		SD %	D %	N %	A %	SA %	Mean	SD
1	You are satisfied with your current job	12	18	44	22	6	2.91	1.04
2	On job, you know what exactly is expected from you	14	28	37	15	6	2.72	1.07
3	At the place where you work, you are treated with respect	2	33	42	20	3	2.87	.83
4	You trust the management at the place where you work	30	38	14	10	8	2.31	1.28
5	You feel proud to work for your present employer	6	14	26	44	10	3.37	1.03
6	The physical working condition is conducive	2	9	21	32	36	3.94	1.02
7	Employees are satisfied with their work schedule and rest	10	14	38	36	2	3.07	1.00
8	The safety of workers is one of the major priorities with management where you work	14	14	24	28	20	3.36	1.03
9	Employees and management work together to ensure the safest possible working conditions	14	14	24	28	20	3.25	1.32
10	There are no occupational hazards and accidents in your organization	50	26	10	10	4	2.11	1.36
11	There are no significant compromises/ shortcuts taken when worker safety is at stake	16	18	36	18	2	2.63	1.03
12	Employees are trained to do their work safely and competitively	10	28	28	14	10	3.05	1.12
13	Your productivity is utilized fully at your workplace	18	38	32	2	10	2.48	1.12

	Job Satisfaction	SD %	D %	N %	A %	SA %	Mean	SD
1	Your remuneration is at par with your assigned job, experience and ability	14	14	26	28	18	3.19	1.31
2	The chances for promotion are good and handled fairly	4	26	36	24	10	3.11	1.00
3	You receive enough help and equipment to get the job done	10	18	30	35	7	3.12	1.10
4	You have freedom to take decision for your own work	18	38	32	8	4	2.37	.90
5	You receive variety of fringe benefits	34	44	6	12	4	2.31	1.40
6	The working environment is far better as compared to other companies of the same industry	14	20	26	26	14	3.23	1.09
7	You believe to have ample growth opportunities in term of designation and remuneration	6	40	34	18	2	2.70	.90
8	You believe to have good facilities/opportunities for individual creativity and self- improvement in your organization	2	22	28	40	8	3.28	.96
9	You believe to be benefitted by the quality of training programs conducted for you	32	36	38	10	4	2.59	.97
10	Training programs help you to develop desired competitive skills and knowledge about your work	36	32	28	4	0	2.19	1.25
11	Job in this organization enhances your social prestige	28	36	24	8	4	2.59	.97

- There is a significant relationship between age and adequate compensation; however the age and the other dimensions of quality of work life such as safe and healthy working conditions, opportunities for development, opportunities for growth and security, social integration, and quality of work life feelings do not have a direct relationship.
- There is a strong relationship between years of experience and adequate and fair compensation; There is a significant relationship between respondent's income and safe and healthy working conditions, opportunities for development, opportunities for growth and security, constitutionalism and quality of work life feelings;
- However there is no significant relationship between respondent's income and the other dimensions of quality of work life such as adequate and fair compensation, and social integration. There is a significant relationship between respondent's family income and healthy working conditions, social integration safe and quality of work life feelings;

	Socialization	SD %	D %	N %	A %	SA %	Mean	SD
1	You share harmonious relationship with your colleagues	10	14	38	36	2	3.07	1.00
2	Your decisions are being effected by the opinions of your colleagues	10	20	32	28	10	3.06	1.07
3	The behavior of your colleagues is same at the work place and otherwise	14	36	34	8	8	2.49	.97
4	Your superiors do not like to socialize with you outside the work place	10	18	30	36	6	3.07	1.00
5	Your subordinates are apprehensive in discussing matters which are not official	10	27	33	30	12	2.48	1.12
6	You carry positive attitude towards job	2	8	30	40	20	3.56	1.03
7	There is a sense of single community among the employees in your organization	6	22	24	30	18	3.12	1.02

- 40% of the respondents were found to perceive high level of quality of work life with regard to adequate and fair compensation and safe and healthy working conditions.
- 37.5% were found to perceive high level of quality of work life with regard to opportunities for development and opportunities for growth and security.
- (47.5%) of the respondents were found to perceive high level of quality of work life with regard to social integration.
- 50% of the respondents were found to perceive high quality of work life with regard to constitutionalism.
- 60 % of the respondents perceive high quality of work life with regard to work and total space.
- 40% of the respondents perceive high quality of work life with regard to social relevance and working life. Only 37.5% of the respondents were found to perceive quality of work life with regard to quality of work life feeling.

Analysis of Demographic and Professional Information

- 53 % of respondents had finished their Under Graduation courses, 34 % had finished their schooling and remaining 13 % of the respondents had finished their Post-Graduation courses.
- 62% of the respondents belong to urban areas, 18 % of the respondents belong to rural areas and remaining 20% of the respondents are from semi urban areas.

- 74% of the respondents are males and only 36% of the respondents are female.
- 22% of the respondents are clerks, 37.5% of the respondents are Executives, 22.5% of the respondents belong to supervisory level and 20% of the respondents belong to managerial level.
- 32.5% of the respondents belong to HR department, 27.5% of the respondents belong to operations, 28% of the respondents belong to marketing and 12% of the respondents belong to administration.

Conclusion

The quality of work life approach considers people as 'asset' to the organization rather than 'costs'. Employees should love their work and love the place they work with the quality of work life. Better quality of work life promotes human dignity and growth, collaborative work, compatibility of people, organizational goals, etc. Only when the right ambience is provided to the employees, they will be able to deliver their goods effectively and efficiently. As a result, employees become satisfied, motivated, involved and committed individuals with respect to their lives at work. In the present study, about 48% of the respondents are satisfied with the quality of work life in the Neyveli Lignite Corporation. The employees have a few problems with the quality of work life such as inconsistent promotion policy, lack of measures for the improvement of standard of living, inadequate measures for control and reduction of stress, lack of encouragement to experiment with new methods, inadequate counseling, lack of appreciation of the good work of subordinates, lack of top management's understanding of subordinates' problems, injustice and discrimination of employees, absence of strong mechanism for grievance redressal, inadequate training programs, poor working conditions and lack of employees' participation. To ensure a positive outcome, attention to the factors identified in the suggested framework is important for improved quality of work life.

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